

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D6.5

**General robot control station (second
version)**

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
ETHZ	ETH Zurich
gRCS	Generic Robot Control Station
ID	Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
IVP	Inspection and Visualization Portal
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MAVLink	Micro Air Vehicle Link
mRCS	Mission-Specific Robot Control Station
PCD	Point Cloud Data (file format)
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
STL	STereoLithography (file format)
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USE	University of Seville
UUID	Universally Unique IDentifier
UT	Ultrasonic Testing
WP	Work Package
WTR	Waygate Technologies Robotics

Glossary of Terms

Table 1. Glossary of terms.

Term	Explanation
Asset data	Any data related to a physical asset, describing its characteristics and (spatial) features. This data will vary, depending on asset type. For example: manufacturer, material, year built, length, volume, operating temperature, 3D models, 2D drawings
Asset information	Used interchangeably with asset data
Inspection plan	A plan to perform inspections on an asset. Also known as Inspection Test Plan (ITP). The list of tasks is determined by the inspection strategy chosen (e.g. periodical, risk-based, etc). An inspection plan may include a variety of inspection tasks. Not all of these inspection tasks may be performed by robotic solutions.
Inspection type	The inspection type indicates the technology/methodology used to perform an inspection task. Inspection types can be: Visual inspection, UT 4 point measurements, UT Grid measurements, CR, Dye Penetrant etc.
Inspection location	An asset can have Inspection Locations. Locations can be defined as early as the design phase of the asset (e.g. Corrosion Monitoring Locations (CML)). Other locations are a result of earlier inspection findings, defects or assessments or are created ad-hoc, during inspection. Typically, an Inspection location is being revisited periodically, to trend the defect development. This means, all findings/measurements need to be linked to an Inspection location.
Inspection tasks	An inspection task is the combination of an inspection type performed at and inspection location. This also includes cleaning/preparatory tasks.
Inspection equipment	The Inspection equipment consists of sensors and robotics system used to perform the inspection. Data includes sensor type, make, calibration etc.
Mission	The deployment of a robotic solution in the field to perform one or more inspection tasks. A mission requires mobilization/demobilization of inspection equipment and personnel.
Mission plan	The full set of documents and data that is gathered/captured before, during and after a mission. See Table 37 in D3.1 for more details.
Mission definition	The inspection tasks from an inspection plan that are in scope of a mission.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

Based on the generic Robot Control Station (gRCS) architecture and operation outlined in D6.1 (General robot control station (first version)), the gRCS has been improved and finalized all the required functionalities during this second development phase of the project. In addition, the interfaces with the robotic systems and the I&M platform have been modified to address the needs of the project after the experience gathered during the first validation set of experiments and pilots.

Then, this deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within task T6.1 (“General robot control station development”) during its second period of activity after the first large-scale pilot demonstrations.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the graphical, usability and feasibility improvements made to the gRCS with respect to D6.1. These improvements come from a compilation of bugs and proposals collected from the project partners after the first demonstration pilots.

Section 3 describes the modifications and improvements made to the communications interfaces, both towards the robotic vehicles and the I&M portal.

Finally, section 4 presents some conclusions and the repository where the gRCS has been released as open-source software.

2. Improvements in the graphical user interface

The user interface described in D6.1 was a preliminary version where we wanted to fulfill all the necessary functionalities for the project. However, it was not used or evaluated by anyone, other than the programmers themselves.

Then, the gRCS was shared with partners working with robotic vehicles so that they could use it during the execution of the first large-scale pilot demonstrations. While it functioned adequately, different partners reported a number of bugs and made suggestions for improving various aspects.

The gRCS aims to be used in different scenarios and by different operators in the simplest possible way, so it should be adapted to different use cases' needs, as depicted in Figure 1. This section covers the improvements that have been implemented after collecting all the feedback from partners.

Figure 1. Integration of gRCS with multiple robotic vehicles during inspections of a tunnel (top left), vessel (top right), refinery (bottom left) and viaduct (bottom right).

2.1 Bug reports after first pilot demonstrations

As mentioned above, following the first large-scale pilot demonstrations, partners with robotic vehicles were requested to provide a report on the gRCS. This report comprised a compilation of identified bugs within the application, along with recommendations and suggestions for improving its functionality to optimize the operation of their robotic vehicles. This made the application more generic and useful for most robotic vehicles, from crawlers to aerial robots.

Table 2 shows a compilation of these reported bugs and corresponding improvement suggestions by each partner. The table includes all those that have been considered and implemented in the new gRCS version.

Table 2. Bugs or improvements reported from each partner.

Id	Partner	Bug/Improvement Description	Solution
01	ETHZ	The operator must not be able to change the position of the ACTION type waypoints in the ‘Waypoints Editor’ widget.	The option of changing the position of the ACTION type waypoints is disabled.
02	ETHZ	Allow negative values in the parameters of the High-Level Actions.	The spin box of each command parameter now supports negative numbers.
03	WTR	Hide the Home position asset (disc with arrow).	Implemented through the visualization configuration dialog.
04	WTR	Modify Inspection Locations transparency (points and areas).	Implemented through the visualization configuration dialog.
05	WTR	Check if it is useful to show the UUID in the waypoint labels.	Added the option to show or hide them in the visualization config dialog.
06	WTR	It is not possible to delete ACTION waypoints by right-clicking on them and using the drop-down menu.	It is possible to delete action waypoints using the drop-down menu.
07	WTR	The pointcloud (generated from the surface model) appears overly coarse for a small asset. To facilitate clicking on the points, we had to enlarge them significantly, resulting in the loss of visibility of assets details.	The number of points used when sampling a mesh to a point cloud is proportional to the mesh size.
08	WTR	Be able to modify the size of the waypoints label and the global frame axis in the 3D viewer.	Implemented through the visualization configuration dialog.
09	USE	When uploading post-mission data, sometimes the same data is uploaded twice in a row. This generates an error that the ‘sync_id’ already exists in the portal, but the data has been uploaded correctly.	It has been checked and ensured that data is uploaded only once to avoid this conflict.

2.2 Improvements from D6.1

This section presents and details the improvements made with respect to the gRCS reported in D6.1 at the graphic interface level. Most of these new functionalities and enhancements are based on the feedback reports discussed in Section 2.1.

2.2.1 Load & save downloaded Inspection Plans

As already mentioned, using gRCS in different scenarios and by different operators has implied the development of new functionalities. Therefore, it was necessary to carry out the inspection offline, without needing an Internet connection that could not be available at the inspection site. For this purpose, a system for saving and loading previously downloaded Inspection Plans was implemented. The goal of this functionality is to download the desired inspection plan in the office where a reliable Internet connection is available prior to going to the inspection site. Subsequently, at the inspection site, the operator can seamlessly work with the previously downloaded inspection plan.

To achieve this, upon downloading an Inspection Plan, a corresponding JSON file is stored on the local disk. Moreover, each time a new asset associated with an inspection plan must be downloaded, a JSON file is also saved on disk, containing the asset's information and the asset itself in '.bin' format. In this way, a local folder structure allows to easily associate Inspection Plans with their corresponding assets and waypoints lists. This is automatically created when the Inspection Plan is successfully downloaded.

Then, the operator can load one of the previously downloaded inspection plans using the 'Load inspection plan from local' button. The selection dialog with an example of different downloaded inspection plans is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Load inspection plan dialog.

2.2.2 Pointcloud asset cutter tool

There are some use cases, considered in PILOTING, in which the interior of an asset must be inspected, which led to the need to create missions inside the asset itself. To facilitate the task of crating the inspection mission, it was decided to develop a tool that is able to cut the asset 3D model.

Using the ‘Cut Pointcloud’ button, a dialog pops up like the one shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Point cloud asset cutter tool dialog.

As shown in the dialog, the point cloud asset can be cut in the three global axes (X, Y, Z). Using the selector of the axis and the horizontal slider, the operator can cut the asset pointcloud. In fact, the changes made by the cuts are being shown in real-time. Moreover, it is possible to change the direction of the cut (negative or positive). An example of a cut using this tool is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Pointcloud cut example.

If the operator makes a mistake during any of these cuts, it is possible to restore the asset point cloud using the ‘Restore Cloud’ button. Furthermore, if the operator wants to hide the complete pointcloud asset, the ‘Hide Cloud’ button can be used.

2.2.3 *Different asset formats*

At the first stage of the development of the gRCS, the supported format for the asset was the ‘Point Cloud Data’ format, i.e. ‘.pcd’. However, there are robots that do not work with pointclouds; instead, they need a mesh asset to work. Since the gRCS should work with as most as possible robotic systems, a conversion tool has been developed.

To perform this conversion, if the downloaded asset point cloud is a mesh file (i.e. ‘.stl’), the mesh is sampled to a specific number of points directly related to the dimensions of this mesh, and loaded as a point cloud.

Moreover, when an asset with different supported formats is downloaded, a dialog pops up, as shown in Figure 5. Using this dialog, the operator can choose between the different assets to download.

Figure 5. Asset formats selection.

2.2.4 *Visualization improvements.*

The gRCS should be a user-friendly interface to be able to plan and monitor inspection operations. The visualization needs to be adapted based on the specific asset or robotic vehicle being utilized. For example, the scale is not the same when inspecting the inside of a fuel tank, a viaduct, or a refinery. In this way, different visualization improvements have been integrated. Using the ‘Configure Visualization Parameters’ button, a dialog pops up as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Visualization configuration dialog.

The main visualization changes of the gRCS are presented below, which depend on the following selected or modified options:

- The ‘Grid plane’ option allows the user to show/hide the floor grid, as shown in Figure 7. This is useful when you do not have a ground, as in vessel tanks.

Figure 7. Show grid (left) vs. Hide grid (right).

- The ‘Items text’ option allows the user to show/hide all the items text in visualization, as shown in Figure 8. When you have many inspection points or waypoints in a confined space, displaying the text can be annoying and/or useless.

Figure 8. Show text (left) vs. Hide text (right).

- The ‘Global frame axis’ option allows the user to show/hide the global frame, as shown in Figure 9.

If the asset is small and just its origin coincides with the axis, it can be annoying to have the global axis in the middle. So, it is convenient to be able to hide it when the axis references are clear.

Figure 9. Show global frame axis (left) vs. Hide global frame axis (right).

- The ‘Home Position’ option allows the user to show/hide the home position, as shown in Figure 10. Once placed and sent to the robot, the operator may not want to have the mesh always defining the “home position” on the display. This is why it is possible to hide it. The “home position” will be automatically displayed again whenever you enter home editing mode, even if it is deselected.

Figure 10. Show home (left) vs. hide home (right).

- The ‘Waypoint Size Scale’ option allows the user to change the waypoint size scale, as shown in Figure 11.

This is related to the asset size; if the asset is very large, increasing the scale of the axes that define the waypoints might be beneficial for improved visualization.

Figure 11. Waypoint size scale modification.

- The ‘Inspection Point Size Scale’ option allows the user to change the inspection point size scale, as shown in Figure 12.

If the points to be inspected are very small and concrete, it could be convenient to modify their scale to have more precision. This makes easier to monitor the robotic vehicle at work.

Figure 12. Inspection point size scale modification.

- The ‘Inspection Location Transparency’ option allows the user to change the transparency of the inspection points and areas, as shown in Figure 13.
If the asset has a high density of points, it would be complex to visualize the inspection points or areas. For this reason, the possibility of modifying the transparency of the points has been enabled.

Figure 13. Inspection point transparency.

- The ‘PointCloud Points Size’ option allows the user to change the size of the points of the asset pointcloud, as shown in Figure 14.
When you have very few points in a very large space, or many points in a very small space, it is convenient to control the size of the waypoints that define the pointcloud. This facilitates the task of designing routes for robotic vehicles.

Figure 14. Same asset with different point cloud size.

- The ‘Point Cloud Color Style’ option allows the user to change the style of the pointcloud between RGB8 and flat colours.
When the pointcloud does not contain the RGB field, it may be convenient to modify its colour to improve the visualization of the asset. If the user selects flat colour, the pointcloud colour

can be changed using the ‘Select Color’ button. Figure 15 shows an example of a pointcloud with the colour changed.

Figure 15. Color selector dialog (left) and flat color pointcloud (right).

2.2.5 *Advanced planned trajectory*

In the first version of gRCS, waypoints could only be placed in the 2D plane or on flat surfaces perpendicular to the waypoints with fixed orientation or heading, which turned out to be appropriate for large robots, such as aerial robots or terrestrial robots. However, designing an inspection path in a user-friendly approach for smaller robots, such as crawlers, becomes more complex and unintuitive with the previous limitation on the placing of the waypoints.

To simplify this, two functionalities have been added:

- ‘Waypoint heading’ dialog: this dialog allows to modify the heading of the waypoints placed perpendicular to the surfaces. This helps to easily control the heading of the waypoint by using a dial. In this way, the orientation of the front of the robotic vehicle can be set to where is needed at each waypoint.
- Auto-heading waypoint mode: A new mode for generating waypoints has been created, offering the ability to enable or disable it as needed. When this mode is enabled, placing a waypoint automatically adjusts the orientation of the previous waypoint to point directly towards it. Consequently, each waypoint faces the next, ensuring that the robotic vehicle maintains a consistent heading along its designated route, as illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Route design using auto-heading functionality.

3. Improvements in the communication interfaces

The communication interfaces with the robotic vehicles were presented in the previous version of the gRCS (D6.1). Nevertheless, this was the initial approach to the creation of the library.

During the integration weeks with the robotic vehicles, it was necessary to modify and improve this communication library. Due to the needs of the different robots, the interface with robotic systems has been adapted to add these functionalities. Thanks to the use of MAVLink as the communication protocol, this adaptation is flexible and scalable, and only requires adding new messages that meet the needs of our custom functionalities.

Regarding the communications with the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer (DDHL), a series of changes have been made with respect to the preliminary version. These changes are in the data model exchanged between the gRCS and the DDHL, and in the endpoints consumed.

3.1 Interface with robotics systems

This section details the modifications made to the interfaces with the robotic systems prompted by identified needs during the integrations.

These enhancements include the addition of an identifier to synchronize generic and mission-specific data, as well as the creation of new types of commands tailored to the requirements of the robotic vehicles and the I&M platform.

3.1.1 *Sync ID to associate generic and specific data*

The ‘sync id’ is a unique number which synchronizes the generic post-mission data generated by the gRCS and the specific post-mission data generated by each robotic system in the DDHL. The functionality of this identifier is also described in Section 3.2.13.2.1.

Since this ‘sync id’ must be shared with the robotic system, the WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT message, used to upload the waypoint list to the robot, has been modified by adding the ‘sync_id’ field. The new adapted WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT message is shown below:

Table 3. WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT message.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
plan_uuid	char[37]	Identifier of the associated inspection plan

sync_id	uint32_t	Identifier of the synchronization token for gRCS and mRCS mission results merging
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3.1.2 *Inspection Task type UUID added*

In an inspection plan, each inspection task can have a different type, i.e. ‘Visual Inspection’, ‘Ultrasonic Inspection’, ‘Structured Light’, etc. These task types are assigned a unique identifier.

This information must be shared with the robotic system, in order to perform the correct inspection task type. To send this information to the robotic system, the WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM message has been modified by adding a ‘task_type_uuid’ field.

Table 4. WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM message.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
task_id	uint32_t	Identifier of the associated inspection task
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero. Increases monotonically for each waypoint, with no gaps in the sequence (0,1,2,3,4)
task_uuid	char[37]	Identifier of the associated inspection task
task_type_uuid	char[37]	Identifier of the associated inspection task type
command	uint16_t	The scheduled action for the waypoint (see MAV_CMD enum)
autocontinue	uint8_t	Autocontinue to next waypoint
param1	float	PARAM1 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param2	float	PARAM2 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param3	float	PARAM3 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param4	float	PARAM4 (see MAV_CMD enum)
x	float	PARAM5: x position in meters

y	float	PARAM6: y position in meters
z	float	PARAM7: z position in meters

3.1.3 *Redefinition of waypoints types*

Each MAVLink message has a predefined payload and, when sending waypoints to robotic vehicles, it is necessary to send a specific set of parameters. For this reason, after a series of iterations, a consensus was reached for the definition of the missions.

For this purpose, two types of waypoints are finally defined: POSE and ACTION.

- **POSE Waypoints:** these waypoints are defined as waypoints of transit, containing position and orientation information. This requires defining both the position and the orientation in the fixed MAVLink payload, so they can also be used as auxiliary waypoints to define orientations at a specific location. Figure 17 shows examples of this type of waypoints, represented with an axis. This type of waypoint is associated with the MAVLink command ‘MAV_CMD_NAV_WAYPOINT_QUATERNION’.
- **ACTION Waypoints:** these waypoints can only be placed on inspection locations, containing a position and four free parameters, which partners with robotic vehicles can fill according to their needs. This type of waypoint is associated with the commands defined in Section 0. Figure 17 represents these waypoints with a cube over the inspection point (yellow sphere).

Figure 17. Comparative between types of waypoints.

3.1.4 *MAV_CMD commands to define inspection locations*

In order to define in the Inspection and Visualization Portal (IVP) the inspections to be performed by the robotic vehicles, two types of inspection locations have been defined: Inspection Point and Inspection Area.

The ‘Inspection Point’ allows defining a specific point where performing an inspection is needed. For example, a point where to make a UT measurement, or taking a photo in a specific place. On the other hand, the ‘Inspection Area’ allows defining complete areas to be inspected. With this, it is possible to take measurements or data from larger areas than just a single point.

Therefore, two types of commands have been created to share the inspection locations information downloaded in the gRCS with the robotic vehicles.

- MAV_CMD_NAV_INSP_POINT: to inspect a specific point in the 3D space.

Table 5. MAV_CMD_NAV_INSP_POINT message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Reserved	Reserved
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- MAV_CMD_NAV_INSP_AREA: to inspect an area in 3D space. The area is defined with four consecutive commands, each command representing one of the corners of the area.

Table 6. MAV_CMD_NAV_INSP_AREA message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Reserved	Reserved
2	Reserved	Reserved

3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

3.1.5 *MAV_CMD commands to each robotic vehicle*

Since each robotic vehicle executes some kind of specific task, it has been concluded that it is necessary to create specific MAVLink commands. These commands could be associated with the previously defined ACTION type waypoints.

These types of specific MAVLink commands are defined below:

- **MAV_CMD_TAKE_PHOTO**: this command was created for the robotic vehicles which carry a camera on board. The objective is to determine the precise location at which the picture should be captured. .

Table 7. MAV_CMD_TAKE_PHOTO message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Reserved	Reserved
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- **MAV_CMD_MANIPULATE_VALVE**: the purpose of this command, added for the UGV-Panda Manipulator, is to be able to manipulate a valve in the refineries with a robotic arm.

Table 8. MAV_CMD_MANIPULATE_VALVE message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Turning Angle	Turning angle in radians
2	Turning Direction	Turning direction [1.0 = clockwise; -1.0 = counterclockwise]
3	Reserved	Reserved

4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- **MAV_CMD_PLACE_OBJECT**: this command was introduced for VIAD-DRONE, and its purpose is to place an object in a 3D space.

Table 9. MAV_CMD_PLACE_OBJECT message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Object Type	Object type: [0: Sensor, 1: Sticker]
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- **MAV_CMD_STICK_TO_THE_CEILING**: this command was introduced for the TT-DRONE, and defines the position of the space where the robot should stick to the ceiling of the viaduct structure.

Table 10. MAV_CMD_STICK_TO_THE_CEILING message.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Reserved	Reserved
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved

4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

3.2 Interface with DDHL

The interface with DDHL is based upon RESTful interfaces. During the first iteration of large-scale pilot demonstrations, new functionalities were needed to facilitate the operation of downloading the inspection plans by the operator.

3.2.1 Sync ID creation

As previously mentioned, the ‘sync id’ is a unique identifier that synchronizes the general post-mission data generated by the gRCS with the specific post-mission data generated by the robotic system. This identifier is necessary because an operator may create different missions using the same inspection plan and upload the post-mission data (specific and generic) to the DDHL. However, the DDHL cannot link both types of post-mission data without this identifier. By using the ‘sync id’, the DDHL can associate all the post-mission data belonging to the same inspection mission. The gRCS is responsible for creating the sync ID every time the operator creates a new mission, and this identifier is shared with the robotic system. When both types of post-mission data are uploaded to the DDHL, the ‘sync id’ links them.

Figure 18. Sync ID workflow.

3.2.2 DDHL configuration

The inspection plans can now be downloaded in two different ways: using an URL and using IP address & port. Figure 19 shows the dialog for configuring the communications to the DDHL.

Figure 19. IP & port and URL DDHL download.

3.2.3 Inspection plans download by site

The inspection plan had to be downloaded through the DDHL using its UUID, so the operator had to access de IVP in order to know the UUID of the desired inspection plan. An example of a UUID is the following ‘eaf4fb71-484d-4dae-a495-28442164c7c0’, which is a rather inconvenient way of handling this download.

A new endpoint has been exposed, so the operator does not need to know the inspection plan’s UUID in order to download it. This endpoint offers all the inspection plans created on each type of site, i.e. ‘Viaduct’, ‘Refinery’ and ‘Tunnel’. Figure 20 shows how the download by site is carried out.

Figure 20. Inspection plans selected by site.

When the operator selects any of the sites, the relevant information on the inspection plans created on this site will be downloaded, so the operator can choose which inspection plan to download. An example of different inspection plans is shown below in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Inspection plans in tunnel site type.

3.2.4 Generic data exchange between gRCS and DDHL

This section details the updates carried out on the data exchanged between the gRCS and the DDHL, with respect to the contents reported in D6.1.

The endpoints used by the gRCS are shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Endpoints used by the gRCS.

Endpoint Name	Request method	Description
apis/Inspectionplan/<str:plan_id>/	GET	Obtain the inspection plan information using its UUID
apis/Inspectionplan/site/<int:site_id>	GET	Obtain a list of inspection plans using its site id. Site_id = { Viaduct = 0, Refinery = 2, Tunnel = 3 }
apis/Mission/gRCS/	POST	Upload the generic post mission data

The current version of the communications exposes two GET methods. The first method allows for requesting an inspection plan based on its UUID. Additionally, a new endpoint was introduced to facilitate requests based on the site type. This allows gRCS users to retrieve an inspection plan without prior knowledge of its specific UUID.

Furthermore, when requesting an inspection plan using any of the aforementioned methods, the gRCS downloads it and generates a JSON file containing the necessary information for local storage on a computer. This enhancement addresses the potential challenge of an unreliable Internet connection at the inspection site, allowing the inspection plan to be saved locally and subsequently loaded based on the data stored within the JSON file.

```
inspectionPlan:
  type: object
  properties:
    Name:
      type: string
    UniqueID:
      type: string
    UpdateDatetime:
      type: string
    CreationDatetime:
      type: string
    Description:
      type: string
    InspectionTasks:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#inspectionTask'
    Asset:
      $ref: '#asset'
```

Figure 22. Inspection Plan Object.

```
inspectionTask:
  type: object
  properties:
    Name:
      type: string
    UniqueID:
      type: string
    UpdateDatetime:
      type: string
    CreationDatetime:
      type: string
    Description:
      type: string
    InspectionLocation:
      $ref: '#inspectionLocation'
    InspectionType:
      $ref: '#inspectionType'
```

Figure 23. Inspection task object.

```
inspectionLocation:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    SubType:  
      type: string  
    properties:  
      $ref: '#properties'
```

Figure 24. Inspection location object.

```
properties:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    depth:  
      type: string  
    height:  
      type: string  
    pitch:  
      type: string  
    posX:  
      type: string  
    posY:  
      type: string  
    posZ:  
      type: string  
    roll:  
      type: string  
    width:  
      type: string  
    yaw:  
      type: string
```

Figure 25. Properties object.

```
inspectionType:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    Name:  
      type: string  
    UniqueID:  
      type: string  
    Description:  
      type: string  
    Properties:  
      type: string
```

Figure 26. Inspection type object.

```
asset:
  type: object
  properties:
    Name:
      type: string
    UniqueID:
      type: string
    Path:
      type: string
    CreationDateTime:
      type: string
    UpdateDateTime:
      type: string
```

Figure 27. Asset object.

Finally, after an inspection mission is completed, the associated data is uploaded to the DDHL through a POST method to the endpoint 'apis/Mission/gRCS/'. The mission JSON used to upload the information is shown below.

```
mission:
  type: object
  properties:
    Name:
      type: string
    SyncId:
      type: string
    CreationTimeStamp:
      type: string
    Description:
      type: string
    InspectionPlanUuid:
      type: string
    LastUpdateTimeStamp:
      type: string
    MissionTasks:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#missionTask'
```

Figure 28. Mission object.

```
missionTask:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    CreationTimeStamp:  
      type: string  
    Description:  
      type: string  
    InspTaskUuid:  
      type: string  
    LastUpdateTimeStamp:  
      type: string  
    Name:  
      type: string
```

Figure 29. Mission task object.

4. Conclusions

This document has presented the improvements and bug fixes made to the gRCS and the communication interfaces during the second phase of the project.

Regarding gRCS, many enhancements have been made based on the feedback obtained during its testing in the first large-scale pilot demonstrators. The first version of the gRCS already demonstrated its high potential and its ability to work in a generic way with a wide range of robotic vehicles. Now, after the feedback and performed modifications, we have improved the user experience and made the interface more user-friendly to facilitate the plan and execution of inspection missions.

With respect to the communications interfaces, adjustments have been implemented based on the feedback obtained from the first experiments. The objective was the same as with the user interface, improve the gRCS solution to improve its usability and user experience.

Finally, it is important to point out that the gRCS software has been released as open-source (as part of the PILOTING I&M platform opensource solution), enabling other users and operators to utilize its immense potential and benefit from its capabilities. The repository URL where the source code can be found is https://github.com/fada-catec/piloting_grcs. It also includes instructions on how to build the software and use the Docker container, and more importantly, it will allow keeping track of bugs and contributions in the future.